

Supplement 1

Protocol

Aim:

Global meta-analysis on ecological impacts of recreational activities on freshwater ecosystems.

Methodology:

Systematic literature research using multiple data bases

We conducted a systematic literature search from November 2018 until February 2019 following the guidelines for systematic research by Siddaway, Wood [1]. We searched both peer-reviewed and grey literature in different languages to compile the best available evidence base. We constructed a search term containing synonyms for recreation AND aquatic AND impacts AND environment. The following search term was used for the literature research in the Web of Science Core collection:

((recreation* leisure (*shore NEAR/1 development) pleasure sport* tourist (human near/1 wildlife) (outdoNEAR/0 activity) (UV NEAR/1 (filter* protection screen)))

AND

(aquatic water* lake* river* stream* freshwater* marine riparian littoral coast* beach* reed* shore*)

AND

(impact* disturb* effect* affect* consequence* comparison* change* modification* alter* influence* behavior* reaction* avoid* survival abundance fitness FID (flight NEAR/0 (initiation NEAR/0 distance)) population biodiversity conservation stress pressure trample* litter* community assemblages introduction toxic pollution eutrophication (nutrient NEAR/1 input) endocrine reproducti*)

AND

(biodiversity (species NEAR/1 richness) sediment* (water NEAR/0 (quality chemistry)) ecolog* animal* vegetation plant* macrophyte* wildlife *bird* *fowl mammal* fish* crayfish amphibia* reptile* insect* *invertebrat* habitat* biotop* ecosystem* invasive (food NEAR/0 web)))

NOT medic* NOT antibiotic* NOT cattle NOT coli

We excluded literature regarding human health issues (e.g. E.coli) and where source of pollution was associated with wastewater treatment plants. There was thus no relationship to recreation.

We adapted the search terms for seven different literature databases and yielded 13.115 articles: Web of Science Core Collection n = 6.937, Scopus n = 4.206, BioOne n = 1.056, Conservation Evidence n = 39, BASE n = 596, and ProQuest n = 45. List of all search terms for each data base is given in the Appendix.

Exclusion criteria:

We excluded articles that did not study

- (1) impacts of recreational activities,
- (2) impacts on other systems than aquatic ecosystems,
- (3) impacts that were not ecological.
- (4) articles of other languages than English, German, French or Spanish as these were not accessible to the authors.

For consumptive activities (angling and hunting) we excluded impacts on target species to ensure comparability of effect sizes and because these direct impacts (e.g., of angling on fish or of hunting on waterfowl) are far beyond disturbance impacts. We were only interested in the ecological impacts other than impacts on target species, which are pretty obvious and already intensively studied.

Even though we wanted to focus on freshwater ecosystems in the first place, we did not exclude marine studies during title and abstract screening, as we were afraid, that the number of studies focusing on freshwater ecosystems might not be sufficient. Therefore we included marine terms in our search term. While we started full text screening, we tried to estimate the approximate number of papers with effect sizes if we would include both marine and freshwater studies by accounting for exclusion rate (which ranged at this stage between 30-60 %) and percentage of studies from which data for effect sizes (ES) calculation could be derived (30 – 30 % of papers examined at this stage). As number of studies seemed promising, we decided to focus solely on freshwater systems. Therefore, we excluded another 3.526 marine articles.

The following studies were retained for meta analytical modelling: (1) studies that compared organism/ecosystem responses to the presence of recreational activities (impact) vs. lack of the recreational activity (control), (2) studies that compared organism/ecosystem responses to different intensities of a recreational activity (observational study), (3) organism/ecosystem responses to a specific compound/substance/aspect that is referred to a specific recreational activity compared to a control within an experiment in situ or in mesocosms.

PRISMA 2009 Flow Diagram

Figure S 2: PRISMA flow diagram showing the number of records and articles in each step during identification, screening, eligibility and including of literature. Flow chart provided by: Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG, The PRISMA Group (2009). Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses: The PRISMA Statement. PLoS Med 6(7): e1000097. doi:10.1371/journal.pmed1000097

Data extraction

We extracted information and data from original studies to calculate effect sizes and variables to test our hypotheses and to control for possible moderators as confounding factors. We prepared a coding sheet with variables regarding study identifiers, data set, study design, affected biotope, affected taxa, impact studied, response measures, outcome information and values to calculate effect sizes. If given, we also extracted effect sizes directly from studies. For most of categorical variables we used predefined categories, to ensure a standardized coding procedure. To achieve even more standardization and ensure comparability among studies, each study was recoded a second time by the first author and (missing) values added or corrected if needed. All variables and respective predefined categories are given in table 1.

Table 1: Coding procedure. We extracted information and data from original publication with a predefined coding sheet with Variables and possible predefined categories (for categorical variables).

Section	Variable	Categories	Meaning	Explanation / Comments
Identifiers	Coder ID	MS	Malwina Schafft	Only first coder is entered here, because all studies have been coded a second time by MS to ensure a standardized coding procedure for all studies.
		NM	Nora Meyer	
		BW	Benjamin Wegener	
	Study ID			We assigned each study an individual number which we called study ID and used this as a categorical variable as a random effect in the meta-analytical modelling processes to account for multiple effect sizes per study, as these are not independent from each other if they originate from the same study
	Entity writing the publication	1	academic	
		2	governmental	
		3	business	
		4	non-profit	
		41	environmental NGO	
		42	fisheries NGO	
5		other		
Journal	Journal name			
	999	not sure/not mentioned		
Study/Data set	Publication type	1	journal	
		2	book	
		3	book chapter	
		4	report	
		5	conference proceedings	
		6	published (other)	
		7	unpublished (thesis)	
		8	unpublished (other)	
	Peer reviewed	1	no	
		2	yes	
999		not sure		

	english	english	categories not predefined, to have the option to enter other languages, if data extraction possible
Language	german	german	
	french	french	
	spanish	spanish	
	...	other	
Study type	A	After impact only	No complete coding of A-studies, if effect sizes cannot be calculated due to missing comparator
	CI	control vs. impact	
	BA	before vs. after without control	
	G	gradient response model	
Study main focus on impact of water-based recreational activity/ disturbance	BACI	Before after control impact	
	1	no	
	2	yes	
Dataset name	name		only if given
Fieldwork/ sampling START	date	start of sampling with exact date, month or year	
	999	not sure/not mentioned	
Fieldwork/ sampling END	date	end of sampling with exact date, month or year	
	999 - not sure/not mentioned	999	not sure/not mentioned
Country	List of country codes here: https://unstats.un.org/unsd/tradekb/Knowledgebase/50347/Country-Code		
Latitud	https://www.latlong.net/degrees-minutes-seconds-to-decimal-degrees		
Longitud			
Continent			
Study design	1	temporal randomized	
	2	spatial randomized	
	4	temporal not randomized	
	5	spatial not randomized	
	999	not sure	
Number of control sampling units	the number of real replication (sites/water bodies for spatial or years for temporal separation - not pseudo replication (repetition of sampling of same Population, Individuals in spatial separation, number of sites on water body level etc.. Must not be equal to sample size (if number of control sampling units Zero - no coding necessary		
Number of impact sampling units	the number of real replication (see 'Number of control sampling units')		
Replication of gradient response units	the number of real replication (see 'Number of control sampling units')		

	Confounding factors	1	no	controlled for environmental variables / habitat differences?
		2	yes	
	Location	1	field	
		2	laboratory	
	Scale	1	water body	comparison of whole water bodies
		2	Zone	comparison of zones within a water body
		999	not sure/not applicable	not applicable e.g. in laboratory studies
		1	no	After title and abstract screening we decided to include only freshwater systems as this was the original aim of our study. When we started our analysis we were worried that the sample size would not be sufficient for a focus on freshwater ecosystems and this is why we started with a broader approach and this is why we have this category in our coding procedure.
	Feshwater	2	yes	
		999	not sure	
		1	marine	
		2	freshwater	
		21	lentic	
		211	lake	
	Water body	2111	gravel pit lake	
		212	pond	
		22	lotic	
		221	stream	
		222	river	
		999	not sure/not mentioned	
Biotop		1	beach	
		2	coast	
		3	estuary	
		4	open water	
		5	sand bank/tidelands	
		6	mudflats	
	Habitat	7	sand dunes	
		8	herbaceous bank	
		9	woody bank	
		10	reeds	
		11	urban/paved banks	
		12	undefined bank/shore/riparian habitat	
		13	benthos	
		999	not sure/not mentioned	
	Size of water body			with scale, as we did not intend to use this information in a systematic way we did not make the effort to recalculate given size into a standardized scale, instead we used the information as given in the manuscript or tried to find out the size of the water body in online research
Taxa	Taxonomic group	1	invertebrates	
		2	fish	

		3	amphibians	
		4	reptiles	
		5	birds	
		6	mammals	
		7	plants	
		8	Phytoplankton	
		9	Zooplankton	
		999	not sure/ not mentioned/not applicable	not applicable for environmental compartments
	Species/taxa		scientific name	for environmental category environmental compartment
		1	angling	
		1.2	angling on boat	
		2	walking	
		3	dog walking	
		4	horse riding	
		5	biking	
		6	vehicle (on land)	
		7	swimming/bathing	
		8	snorkeling	
		9	diving	
		10	boating	
		11	canoe	
		12	paddle boat	
		13	row boat	
		14	motor boat	
		14.1	yacht	
	Recreational activity	15	speed boat	
Impact		16	jet ski	
		17	water ski / wake boarding	
		18	surfing	
		19	kite surfing	
		20	stand-up paddling	
		21	rafting	
		22	model boat	
		23	picnicking	
		24	camping	
		25	hunting	
		26	wildlife observation	
		27	multiple	
		28	trail use	
		29	hanging out on the beach	
		999	not sure	
	Concentration/Intensity			Concentration of chemicals (toxicity tests or intensity of recreational activity (if given with scale! NA - not mentioned / not sure

	1	no
Activity motorized	2	yes
	999	not sure
	1	shore
Location of activity	2	riparian
	3	open water
	999	not sure
Impact studied	presence	
	noise	e.g. recordings
	trampling	
	paddling	
	pollution /	
	toxicity	
	damage /	
	injury	
	extraction / consumption	
	mortality	
	999	not sure /not mentioned

Impact specification

especially for laboratory experiments which chemical reagent or which aspect of the activity was the focus

Comments **Any** **other**
comments **related**
to the publication or
the dataset

Response **Response measured**

avoidance
time budgets
physiological
abundance
reproduction
community
biodiversity
water
chemistry
pollution
soil
compaction

			<p>exact wording e.g.:</p> <p>avoidance: AD (alert distance), FID (flight initiation dist.), DF (distance fled)</p> <p>time budgets: immobile time, locomotion time, alert/vigilance time, vocalisation time, resting time, foraging/feeding time, grooming time, comfort behaviour time, social behaviour time, aggression time, play time</p> <p>physiological: heart rate, metabolic rate, mineral balance, blood parameters, injuries/healing wounds, glucocorticoids, energy balance, parasite load, body mass/size/condition</p> <p>abundance: e.g. vegetation cover, number of individuals, pairs</p> <p>reproduction: nest success, number of offspring, reproductive rate</p> <p>community, food web</p> <p>biodiversity: species number</p> <p>water quality/chemistry: turbidity/suspended solids, pH-value, eutrophication, N-input, P-input, C-input</p> <p>behavioural physiological, energetic and genetic impacts. e.g. increased vigilance, flight responses, injuries etc.</p> <p>mortality or impaired recruitment, e.g. number of breeding pairs, overall breeding success, abundance of macrophyte species</p> <p>change in relative abundances taxa, e.g. change of species richness or species composition, introduction of invasive species</p> <p>change affecting environmental compartments and aesthetics, e.g. water turbidity, soil compaction, littering/pollution, eutrophication, reduced vegetation height or cover. This Category was renamed to 'impacts on the environment' during peer review process, this category was not used as level of biological organization any more for resubmission of the manuscript</p>
Response specification			
		1	individual
		2	population
		3	community
Level of biological organization		4	ecosystem
		999	not sure
		+	increase
		-	decrease
		Δ	change
		0	no effect
Direction			What is the sign NOW (Positive or negative), if calculated as it is now (subtract control mean from treatment mean)
		1	positive = positive effect
			negative = negative effect
Outcome		2	positive = negative effect
			negative = positive effect
Meaning		3	change (positive/negative = negative effect)
			Interpretation of effect. For example if response variable is number of dots that indicate sickness of a turtle. More dots in treatment than in control group is + = increase in direction but this increase of sickness is a negative effect and the positive sign of effect size has to be changed to a negative effect (Meaning)
			Scale in which response values are given (e.g. gram (g), meters (m), per cent (%))
Scale			
Control / comparator	Real control?	1	yes
		2	low vs high intensity

	3	not real BA (Before-After)	e.g. comparing days/hours/etc. with and without activity (or low vs. high intensity days/hours/etc.) within the same season - not always coded as 3, sometimes coded as 1 (yes)
	4	comparing different activities, instead of control	
	999	not sure	
	Specify control		To what or to which other recreational activity is it compared to as "control"?
	C - Sample size		extract sample size values
	C - Mean response		extract values of arithmetic mean
	C - SE		extract standard error values
	C - SD		extract standard deviation values
Treatment	T - Sample size		extract sample size values
	T - Mean response		extract values of arithmetic mean
	T - SE		extract standard error values
	T - SD		extract standard deviation values
test-statistics	T-value		
	df	degrees of freedom	
	p-value		
F-test	F-value		
Effect size for standardized mean difference	Cohen's d		in these cells we had a formula to automatically calculate effect sizes of standardized mean differences to check direction (and magnitude) of response variable
	Hedges g		
Control to calculate response ratios	C positive		
	C negative		
Treatment to calculate response ratios	T total		
	T positive (%)		
	T positive (N)		
	T negative		
Effect size (ratio)	Odds ratio		
	Risk ratio		
Gradient response	scale of intensity		e.g. humans per time/area, duration of human presence, amount of noise, speed
	Mean low intensity		We mainly used the cells for standardized mean differences, even for comparison of high vs. low intensities and added information of intensity of different categories (if given) in the impact section in the cell called 'concentration / Intensity' instead of using this section for Gradient response
	Mean high intensity		

	independent/ predictor variable (X name (scale))	
	dependet/ response variable (Y name (scale	
Regression	Standard deviation of dependet variable (Y	We extracted values of results of regression models, even though we were not able to calculate a standardised effect size with these values
	regression coefficient (R^2	
	beta	
	sr^2	
	sample size control	
	sample size treatment	
	x-variable name (scale)	
	y-variable name (scale)	
Correlation	Correlation coefficient (R)	Extract information to be able to calculate Fishers z as effect size
	Variance sample size	
Effect Size (correlation)	Fishers z	
	IRR	
Effect size	95% CI	
	SE	

Appendix 1

Adapted search Terms for each data base:

Colourcoding: Recreation, specific recreational activities, aquatic, impact, ecological

BASE:

(recreation* OR leisure pleasure OR sport* OR tourist OR outdoor activity)(aquatic OR water* OR lake* OR river* OR stream* OR freshwater* OR marine OR riparian OR littoral OR coast* OR beach* OR reed* OR shore*) (reaction* OR avoid* OR survival OR abundance OR fitness OR FID OR conservation OR stress OR pressure OR tramp* OR litter* OR introduction OR toxic OR endocrine reproducti* OR impact* OR disturb* OR effect* OR affect* OR consequence* OR comparison* change* OR modification* OR alter* OR influence*) (biodiversity OR species richness OR community OR water OR quality OR ecolog* animal* OR vegetation OR plant* OR macrophyte* OR wildlife OR *bird* OR *fowl OR mammal* fish* OR crayfish OR amphibia* OR reptile* OR insect* OR *invertebrat* OR habitat* OR biotop* OR ecosystem* OR invasive)

BioOne:

(recreation* OR leisure pleasure OR sport* OR tourist OR outdoor activity)(aquatic OR water* OR lake* OR river* OR stream* OR freshwater* OR marine OR riparian OR littora OR l coast* OR beach* OR reed* OR shore*) (reaction* OR avoid* OR survival OR abundance OR fitness OR FID OR conservation OR stress OR pressure OR tramp* OR litter* OR introduction OR toxic OR endocrine reproducti* OR impact* OR disturb* OR effect* OR affect* OR consequence* OR comparison* change* OR modification* OR alter* OR influence* OR behavio*r) (biodiversity OR species richness OR community OR water OR quality OR ecolog* animal* OR vegetation OR plant* OR macrophyte* OR wildlife OR *bird* OR *fowl OR mammal* fish* OR crayfish OR amphibia* OR reptile* OR insect* OR *invertebrat* OR habitat* OR biotop* OR ecosystem* OR invasive)

ProQuest(ASFA)

recreation* OR leisure pleasure OR sport* OR tourist OR outdoor activity AND (impact* OR disturb* OR effect* OR affect* OR consequence* OR comparison* change* OR modification* OR alter* OR influence* OR behavio*r OR reaction* OR avoid* OR survival OR abundance OR fitness OR FID OR conservation OR stress OR pressure OR tramp* OR litter* OR introduction OR toxic OR endocrine reproducti*) AND (biodiversity OR species richness OR community OR water OR quality OR ecolog* animal* OR vegetation OR plant* OR macrophyte* OR wildlife OR bird* OR fowl OR mammal* fish* OR crayfish OR amphibia* OR reptile* OR insect* OR invertebrat* OR habitat* OR biotop* OR ecosystem* OR invasive)

IGB Library

(entered separately in fields = 3 results) 04.12.18

(recreation* OR leisure OR pleasure OR sport* OR tourist OR outdoor activity) AND (aquatic OR water* OR lake* OR river* OR stream* OR freshwater* OR marine OR riparian OR littora OR coast* OR beach* OR reed* OR shore*) AND (reaction* OR avoid* OR survival OR abundance OR fitness OR FID OR conservation OR stress OR pressure OR traml* OR litter* OR introduction OR toxic OR endocrine reproducti* OR impact* OR disturb* OR effect* OR affect* OR consequence* OR comparison* change* OR modification* OR alter* OR influence* OR behavio*r) AND (biodiversity OR species richness OR community OR water OR quality OR ecolog* animal* OR vegetation OR plant* OR macrophyte* OR wildlife OR *bird* OR *fowl OR mammal* fish* OR crayfish OR amphibia* OR reptile* OR insect* OR *invertebrat* OR habitat* OR biotop* OR ecosystem* OR invasive)

Web of Science:

((recreation* leisure (*shore NEAR/1 development) pleasure sport* tourist (human near/1 wildlife) (outdoNEAR/0 activity) (UV NEAR/1 (filter* protection screen))) AND (aquatic water* lake* river* stream* freshwater* marine riparian littoral coast* beach* reed* shore*) AND (impact* disturb* effect* affect* consequence* comparison* change* modification* alter* influence* behavio*r reaction* avoid* survival abundance fitness FID (flight NEAR/0 (initiation NEAR/0 distance)) population biodiversity conservation stress pressure traml* litter* community assemblages introduction toxic pollution eutrophication (nutrient NEAR/1 input) endocrine reproducti*) AND (biodiversity (species NEAR/1 richness) sediment* (water NEAR/0 (quality chemistry)) ecolog* animal* vegetation plant* macrophyte* wildlife *bird* *fowl mammal* fish* crayfish amphibia* reptile* insect* *invertebrat* habitat* biotop* ecosystem* invasive (food NEAR/0 web))) NOT medic* NOT antibiotic* NOT cattle NOT coli

Scopus:

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (recreation* OR leisure OR (*shore W/1 development) OR pleasure OR sport* OR tourist OR (human W/1 wildlife) OR (outdoor W/0 activity) OR (uv W/1 (filter* OR protection OR screen))) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (aquatic OR water* OR lake* OR river* OR stream* OR freshwater* OR marine OR riparian OR littoral OR coast* OR beach* OR reed* OR shore) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (impact* OR disturb* OR effect* OR affect* OR consequence* OR comparison* OR change* OR modification* OR alter* OR influence* OR behavio*r OR reaction* OR avoid* OR survival OR abundance OR fitness OR fid OR (flight W/0 (initiation W/0 distance))) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (population OR biodiversity OR conservation OR stress OR pressure OR traml* OR litter* OR community OR assemblages OR introduction OR toxic OR pollution OR eutrophication OR (nutrient W/1 input) OR endocrine OR reproducti*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (biodiversity OR (species W/1 richness) OR sediment* OR (water W/0 (quality OR chemistry)) OR ecolog* OR animal* OR vegetation OR plant* OR macrophyte* OR wildlife OR *bird* OR *fowl OR mammal* OR fish* OR crayfish OR amphibia* OR reptile* OR insect*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (*invertebrat* OR habitat* OR biotop* OR ecosystem* OR invasive OR (food W/0 web)) AND NOT TITLE-ABS-KEY (medic* OR antibiotic* OR cattle OR coli)) AND ORIG-LOAD-DATE AFT 1628664649 AND ORIG-LOAD-DATE BEF 1629269448 AND PUBYEAR AFT 2019 AND (EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "MEDI") OR

EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "ECON") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "ENER") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "IMMU") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "BUSI") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "PHYS") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "MATE") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "NEUR") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "PSYC") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "HEAL") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "NURS"))

Conservation Evidence:

<https://www.conservationevidence.com/>

keyword: recreation

habitat: Marine, Coastal, Wetlands, Rivers, Streams, Creeks

threats: Human intrusions & disturbance

Natursport Literaturdatenbank

https://natursportinfo.bfn.de/literaturdatenbank.html?tx_bfnatgis_pi1%5Baction%5D=list&tx_bfnatgis_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=Literatur&cHash=68f5fe2a958ba50173109f3daef60c45

Key words with direct connection to aquatic ecosystems:

aquatic species/habitats/recreational activities:

(236 records)

Schlagworte(Keywords) (alphabetical): Amphibien, Angeln, Bäche und Flüsse, Bäche und Flüsse der Alpen, Bachforelle, Bekassine, Biber, Binnengewässer, Blesralle, Brandgans, Canyoning, Dünen, Edelkrebs, Eiderente, Eisvogel, Enten und Gänse, Felsenküste, Fischadler, Fische, Fischerei, Fischotter, Flußregenpfeifer, Flußseeschwalbe, Flusskrebse, Flußuferläufer, Gänsesäger, Graugans, Graureiher, Großer Brachvogel, Haubentaucher, Hecht, Kamberkrebs, Kanu und Kajak, Kiebitz, Knäckente, Kolbenente, Kormoran, Kranich, Krautiger Ufersaum, Krickente, Küstenseeschwalbe, Lachmöwe, Libellen, Makrozoobenthos, Meeresküsten, Modellboote, Nord- und Ostsee, Rafting, Regenbogenforelle, Reiherente, Ringelgans, Röhrichte, Rohrweihe, Rotschenkel, Rudern, Salzwiesen, Schilfrohrsänger, Seeadler, Seehund, Seen, Segeln, Silbermöwe, Staudenfluren, Stockente, Sturmmöwe, Surfen, Tafelente, Tauchen, Teichrohrsänger, Tümpel, Uferschnepfe, Uferschwalbe, Uferwälder und -gehölze, Wasseramsel, Wassermotorrad, Wasserralle, Wasserski und Parasailing, Wassersport, Wattenmeer, Watvögel, Weiher, Weißwangengans, Wildwasser

Sorted:

- Freizeitaktivitäten: Angeln Canyoning Fischerei Kanu und Kajak Modellboote Rafting Rudern Segeln Surfen Tauchen Wassermotorrad Wasserski und Parasailing Wassersport
- Gewässerlebensräume: Bäche und Flüsse Bäche und Flüsse der Alpen Binnengewässer Dünen Krautiger Ufersaum Meeresküsten Nord- und Ostsee Röhrichte Salzwiesen Seen Staudenfluren Tümpel Uferwälder und -gehölze Wattenmeer Weiher Wildwasser
- Arten: Amphibien Bachforelle Bekassine Biber Blesralle Brandgans Edelkrebs Eiderente Eisvogel Enten und Gänse Fischadler Fische Fischotter Flußregenpfeifer Flußseeschwalbe Flusskrebse Flußuferläufer Gänsesäger Graugans Graureiher Großer Brachvogel Haubentaucher Hecht Kamberkrebs Kiebitz Knäckente Kolbenente Kormoran Kranich Krickente Küstenseeschwalbe Lachmöwe Libellen Makrozoobenthos Regenbogenforelle Reiherente Ringelgans Rohrweihe Rotschenkel Schilfrohrsänger

Seeadler Seehund Silbermöwe Stockente Sturmmöwe Tafelente Teichrohrsänger Uferschnepfe Uferschwalbe Wasseramse
Wasserralle Watvögel Weißwangengans

Google:

(strict length limit allows only very short search terms)

(recreation* (water-based AND recreation)leisure disturb*(human AND disturbance)) AND (water lake river stream (aquatic AND (biodiversity Habitat biotop))

German Search:

Freizeit* Angel* Canyoning Kanu Kajak Modellboot* Rafting Ruder* Segel* Surf* Tauch*
Wassermotorrad Wasserski und Parasailing Wassersport AND Bäche Bach Fluss Flüsse
Binnengewässer Süßwasser Dünen Ufer* Meer* *küste* *see* Röhricht* Salzwiese*
Staudenflur* Tümpel Wattenmeer Weiher Wildwasser AND (Stör* *Wirk*) AND Amphibie*
Säugetier* Fisch* *vögel* Reptil* *invertebrat* Makrozoobenthos Ökosystem Umwelt

Google Scholar:

(same search term as for Google, because of same length limits)

Ca 69.500 results (0,20 Sek.)

(recreation* (water-based AND recreation)leisure disturb*(human AND disturbance)) AND (water lake river stream (aquatic AND (biodiversity Habitat biotop))

Appendix 2

Table 2: List of all relevant literature that was obtained by the systematic literature research. The 94 studies used for meta-analysis are indicated (MA = YES)

Study_ID	Reference	ES
1	Nikolaus, R., Schafft, M., Maday, A., Klefoth, T., Wolter, C. & Arlinghaus, R. 2021 Status of aquatic and riparian biodiversity in artificial lake ecosystems with and without management for recreational fisheries: Implications for conservation. <i>Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems</i> 31, 153-172. (doi: https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.3481).	29
9	Völkl, W. 2010 Die Bedeutung und Bewertung von Baggerseen für Fische, Vögel, Amphibien und Libellen: Vereinbarkeit der fischereilichen Nutzung mit den Anforderungen des Naturschutzes;[Artenvielfalt an und in Baggerseen], Bezirk Oberfranken, Fachberatung für Fischerei.	42
15	Matern, S., Emmrich, M., Klefoth, T., Wolter, C., Nikolaus, R., Wegener, N. & Arlinghaus, R. 2019 Effect of recreational-fisheries management on fish biodiversity in gravel pit lakes, with contrasts to unmanaged lakes. <i>J. Fish Biol.</i> 94, 865-881. (doi: https://doi.org/10.1111/jfb.13989).	-
75	Pedroli, J.-C. 1982 Activity and time budget of tufted ducks on Swiss lakes during winter. <i>Wildfowl</i> 33, 105-112.	4
93	Keller, V. 1989 Variations in the response of great crested grebes <i>Podiceps cristatus</i> to human disturbance—A sign of adaptation? <i>Biological Conservation</i> 49, 31-45.	-

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Appendix 3

Table 3: Study quality measures and according weights and categories. A main criterion to assess study validity was study design. 'Replication of sampling units' as whole water bodies and 'control of confounding factors' could lead to higher quality weight (maximum 1). Weight was halved if low and high intensities were compared instead of a real control and also if effects within a water body were studied instead of a comparison between water bodies. A criterion for randomization was only included to identify high quality studies as a qualitative measure. Weights suggested by Norris, Webb [2] and Christie, Amano [3].

Study design type	Norris, Web [2]	Christie, Amano [3]	Quality weights	Study quality
A - After impact only	1	0.0904	0.0904	low
CI - Control vs impact	2	0.206	0.206	moderate
BA - Before vs after	2	0.226	0.226	moderate
G - Gradient response	3	1	0.3	moderate
BACI – Before-after-control-impact	4	$\frac{1}{1+e^{-\left(\frac{0.661+0.0153 \cdot \ln(n_{Impact\ sites})+0.0647 \cdot \ln(n_{Control\ sites})}{+0.111 \cdot \ln(n_{Control\ sites}) \cdot \ln(n_{Impact\ sites})}\right)}}$	0.4	high
Number of reference/control sampling units				
0	0		+0	low
1	2		+0.2	moderate
>1	3		+0.3	high
Number of impact/treatment sampling units				
0	0		+0	low
1			+0.1	moderate
>1			+0.2	high
2	2			
>2	3			
Replication of gradient-response models				
<4	0			low
4	2		+0.2	moderate
5	4		+0.4	moderate
>5	6		+0.6	high
Controlled for confounding factors				
1 – no			+0	low
2 – yes			+0.1	high
Randomized				
1 – No				moderate
2 – Yes				high
Real control				
1 – yes			1/1	high
2 - low vs high			1/2	low
Scale				
1 - water body			1/1	high
2 – zone			1/2	low

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